

DEFORMATION AND FRACTURE MECHANISMS OF FIBER-REINFORCED TITANIUM ALLOY MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The deformation mechanisms and fracture processes of several fiber reinforced titanium alloy matrix composites are discussed. Based upon the material variables (interfacial properties, fiber strength and matrix toughness), several deformation and fracture mechanism maps under various mechanical loadings have been constructed. The effects of these damage mechanisms on the macroscopic mechanical behavior are also discussed.

KEYWORDS: Metal Matrix Composite, Interfacial Properties, Deformation, Fracture, Fatigue, Fatigue Crack Propagation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber-reinforced titanium alloys and titanium-aluminum intermetallic alloy (Ti_3Al , $TiAl$, $TiAl_3$) matrix composites are promising materials for high temperature structural applications [1,2]. They have a unique combination of several attractive properties including high specific stiffness, high specific strength and excellent environmental stability. Potential applications of these novel materials include gas turbine engines, airframe for hypersonic aircraft and advanced energy conversion systems. As a result, a significant amount of effort has been conducted to develop titanium matrix composite technology. Major progress has been made in developing new fibers, matrix alloys and processing techniques. Various approaches have also been developed to optimize the chemical, physical and mechanical phenomena which occur at the fiber/matrix interface. However, before these materials can be used reliably in structural applications, a comprehensive understanding of deformation and damage mechanisms under static and cyclic loading must be developed.

The mechanisms of damage initiation, growth, and damage accumulation of microscopic flaws which leads to failure of a metal matrix composite is a complicated

process. There are several competing microscopic flaw producing mechanisms including fiber fracture, matrix yielding or cracking, fiber/matrix interfacial debonding, and cracking of the interfacial reaction layer. The occurrence of different failure modes and their interaction depend on a variety of material variables (mechanical properties of the constituents, interfacial conditions between fiber and matrix), geometry conditions (fiber orientation, fiber volume fraction), and loading conditions. The stiffness and strength of the fiber and matrix, the strength distribution of the fibers and the fracture toughness of the matrix are the most important constituent parameters. The interfacial conditions such as residual stresses, fiber/matrix bond strength and post-debond frictional stress also play a critical role in determining the behavior of the composite.

A significant amount of experimental work has been conducted at UCLA to study the fracture behavior and damage mechanisms of several unidirectional titanium alloy matrix composites under static and cyclic loading [3-5]. The key microstructural parameters which dominate the initiation and growth of microscopic damage and fracture processes were determined. Some of the most important results are summarized in the following sections.

2. INTERFACIAL PROPERTIES

2-1 Interfacial Mechanical Properties (Bonding Strength & Frictional Stress)

Table I displays the interfacial bonding strength and frictional stress in several different fiber reinforced Ti alloy matrix composites [3]. Due to excessive interfacial reaction and large thermal expansion mismatch between the fiber and Ti alloy, the interfacial bonding strength and frictional stresses are much higher than that in ceramic matrix composites [6]. The interfacial bonding strength were measured to be from 115 (SCS-6/Ti-25-10) to 275 MPa (B₄C/B/Ti-6-4). Results indicated that the interfacial properties and the location of interfacial debonding will be affected by fiber surface chemistry, matrix microstructure and processing condition. The interfacial bonding strength and frictional stress will significantly affect the fracture behavior of the composites. This will be discussed in detail in a later section. In order to control the chemical reactions and tailor the interfacial properties, a diffusion barrier coating on the fiber surface is needed. The benefit of using a coating layer is clearly illustrated in the TiB₂ coated SCS-6 fiber-reinforced Ti-25-10 composite as shown in Fig. 1. No chemical reaction was detected between the fiber and coating layer. A limited reaction was found between the TiB₂ coating layer and the matrix. This is desired to facilitate efficient load transfer from the matrix to the fiber. When subjected to tensile loading, the brittle TiB₂ layer cracked at the early stages of loading. However, the crack did not propagate into the fiber; instead, it was deflected along the coating/fiber interface. Thus, the strength of the fiber can be preserved.

Fig. 1 Interfacial microstructure and failure mechanism of TiB₂ coated SCS-6/Ti-25-10 composite.

2.2 Influence of Interface Layer Thickness on the Strength of the Reaction Layer and Fiber

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the tensile strength of the interfacial reaction zone and the fiber as a function of the reaction zone thickness in the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 and SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composites, respectively [3,4]. The data was obtained by measuring the multiple cracking length of the interface reaction layer and fiber under mechanical loading and shear-lag analysis [7]. From these results, it is clearly indicated that the tensile strength of the interfacial reaction zone and the SCS-6 fiber decreases rapidly as the thickness of the reaction zone increases. Also, the strength of the reaction zone is much lower than that of the fiber, i.e., the fracture strain of the reaction zone is lower than that of the fiber. The results show that damage initiation of the composite occurred at the interfacial reaction zone under mechanical loading. Fig. 2 also implies that the strength of the interfacial reaction zone can be much higher when the reaction zone is thin ($< 1 \mu\text{m}$). Since the interfacial reaction layer has a lower fracture strain than that of the fiber, it will crack and form a notch on the fiber surfaces during the early stages of mechanical loading. If the interfacial bonding strength is strong, the stress concentration at the cracked interfacial reaction zone would degrade the fiber strength. Ochiai et al. [8] has proposed a fracture model to describe the interface-induced degradation in fiber strength. The fiber strength can be expressed as $\sigma_f = 1/Y * (E_f G_c / \pi C)^{1/2}$, where Y is the geometry factor, E_f is the Young's modulus of the fiber, G_c is critical energy release rate, and C is the reaction zone thickness.

Combining the experimental results and theoretical prediction of the fiber strength, the critical interfacial reaction thickness was found to be $0.93 \mu\text{m}$, as shown in Fig. 3. When the thickness of the reaction zone is below $0.93 \mu\text{m}$, the strength of the SCS-6 fiber will not be affected by the interfacial reaction. Therefore, it is possible to tailor the strength of the reaction zone and fiber by controlling the extent of interfacial chemical reactions.

Fig. 2 Tensile strength of the interfacial reaction layer as a function of reaction layer thickness.

Fig. 3 Fracture strength of the SCS-6 fiber as a function of reaction layer thickness.

3. TENSILE FAILURE MECHANISMS

After the damage initiates at the interfacial reaction layer, the growth of damage near the interfacial region in the unnotched unidirectional titanium matrix composites under tensile loading can be schematically summarized in Fig. 4 [4]. In this diagram, the tensile failure mechanisms near the interfacial region can be classified into six modes based upon the ratio of fiber strength to fiber/matrix interfacial shear strength vs. the toughness of the matrix alloys. For the case of composites with a tough (ductile) matrix (modes B, D and F), cracks which initiate in the interfacial reaction layer are arrested by microyielding of the matrix. In the case of a composite with strong fibers and high interfacial bonding strength (mode D, SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite), interfacial debonding did not occur. However, multiple fracture of the interfacial reaction layer induced by load transfer between the fiber and the matrix will occur before the composite failed. In the case of a composite with strong fibers and low interfacial bonding strength (mode B, as-fabricated SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite), interfacial debonding along the reaction layer and the fiber was observed. There was also multiple fracture of the interfacial reaction layer. In both cases, the composites exhibit extensive plastic deformation of the matrix and a flat fracture morphology without significant fiber pull-out. In the case of a composite with weak fibers and high interfacial bond strength (mode F, B₄C coated B/Ti-6-4 composite), the crack can easily extend to the fiber and cause immediate fracture of the fiber. In ductile matrix composites, the composite exhibited "yielding" behavior before fracture.

For the case of brittle matrix composites (modes A, C and E), the crack which initiated in the interfacial reaction layer will propagate into the matrix. In the composite with strong fibers and high interfacial bonding strength (mode C, SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite

annealed at 500 °C), the crack will not debond the interface. However, after the crack extends into the matrix to form a macrocrack of sufficient size, the stress concentration at the crack-tip will cause fiber failure ahead of the crack-tip. This will lead to catastrophic failure of the composite. In this type of composite, the stress-strain curve is linear up to fracture. In the composite with strong fibers and low interfacial bonding strength (mode A, SCS-6/Ti-25-10 composite annealed at 800 °C), significant debonding will occur. This will lead to extensive delamination and fiber pull-out. This type of composite exhibits a bilinear stress-strain behavior. In the composite with weak fibers and strong interfacial bonding strength (mode E, Al₂O₃/Ti-25-10 composite), the crack which initiates in the interfacial reaction layer will propagate into the fiber and matrix. This leads to catastrophic failure of the composite.

Fig. 4 Tensile failure mechanisms at the interfacial region in the fiber-reinforced Ti alloy matrix composites.

4. FAILURE AND TOUGHENING MECHANISMS AT NOTCHED COMPOSITE

When the notched composites were subjected to mechanical loading, a complicated stress field was induced at the notch-tip. Depending on the interfacial properties and mechanical properties of the constituents, several types of damage will occur at the notch-tip. Based upon experimental observation, the fracture behavior that occurred at the notch-tip in the SCS-6/Ti alloy matrix composite can be schematically plotted as

Fig. 5 Failure mechanisms of the notched specimen in the fiber-reinforced Ti alloy matrix composites.

Fig. 6 Fatigue life diagram of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 and Ti-6-4 composites.

shown in Fig. 5 [5]. Since the SCS-6 fiber is quite strong, discussion is limited to effect of the interfacial bonding strength and matrix toughness on the failure mechanisms. For the composite with low interfacial bonding strength and a brittle matrix (case A, SCS-6/Ti-25-10), the crack deflection, matrix shear failure, interfacial debonding and fiber pull-out were the major failure mechanisms during the crack propagation. For this type of composite, the crack exhibited non-planar crack propagation behavior. The crack initiation is controlled by the fiber strength, interfacial bonding strength and shear strength of the matrix. However, the crack propagation energy will depend on the energy absorbed during the matrix shear failure, crack deflection and branching as well as fiber pull-out.

For the composite with high interfacial bonding strength and a brittle matrix (case B, SCS-6/Ti-15-3 heat-treated at 500 °C), the crack propagated across the matrix and fiber without any interfacial debonding. Only a limited multiple fiber breakage zone was observed. In the absence of the crack tip blunting mechanism (matrix plastic deformation, fiber/matrix interfacial debonding), this type of composite exhibited a rapid crack propagating behavior.

In the case of the composite with a high interfacial bonding strength and a tough matrix (case C, SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite), matrix plastic deformation, multiple fiber breakage, and fiber pull-out were the major failure mechanisms. For this type of composite, the crack exhibits a self-similar crack propagating behavior. The crack initiation is controlled by the fiber strength and the yield strength of the matrix. However, the crack propagation energy will depend on the energy absorbed during matrix plastic deformation, multiple fiber fracture, and fiber pull-out.

5. FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANISMS

The fatigue damage mechanisms and fatigue crack propagation behavior of the SCS-6/Ti alloy matrix composites have also been characterized. For the low cycles fatigue life test, standard plain uncracked specimens were used to obtain the S-N curves. Specimens with a chevron notch perpendicular to fiber direction were used to measure the fatigue crack propagation rate. Some of the fatigue results are summarized in the following sections.

5-1 Low Cycles Fatigue

Fig. 6 shows the S-N curves of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 and Ti-6-4 composite under tension-tension ($R=0.1$, $f=10$ Hz) fatigue loading. From this diagram, the fatigue damage of these unidirectional SCS-6/Ti alloy matrix composites can be classified into three regions: (1) fiber breakage dominated, (2) damage accumulation region (interfacial cracking, matrix cracking & fiber breakage) (3) matrix cracking dominated. Fig. 7 shows typical fatigue fracture surface of these composite at applied maximum stress in

the fiber breakage dominated region ($> 70\%$ tensile strength of the composite). The fracture surface was very similar to that of a static tensile failure except for a few matrix fatigue cracks found randomly distributed around individual fiber. It suggests that the composite failure was controlled by the statistical failure of the fibers.

In the damage accumulation region, the applied maximum stress is higher than that needed to initiate the cracking of the interfacial reaction layer. During the early stages of fatigue loading, the interfacial layer cracked at the edge and center of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 8 and 9. Fig. 8 also shows that the cracks propagated along the matrix. The fibers remained intact with the cracked matrix as the fatigue loading cycles increased. Through the load transfer between the fiber and matrix, multiple matrix cracking would occur. However, the fiber breakage was randomly distributed around the matrix cracking plane. The damage induced by interfacial cracking, matrix cracking and fiber breakage would continue to accumulate until the final fracture of the composite occurred. In this accumulation region, the fatigue damage rate is stress-dependent, i.e. the fatigue life increasing as the applied maximum stress decreases.

In the matrix cracking dominated region, the applied maximum cyclic stress is lower than the cracking stress of the interfacial reaction layer. However, cracks would initiate from the broken fibers and damaged interfacial reaction zone on specimen edges resulting from machining damage and propagate into the matrix. Since the fiber still bridge the cracked matrix, new fatigue cracks would form by the load transfer and result in multiple matrix cracking at the specimen edges. After these nucleation process is saturated, the fatigue life will be spent on the propagating of these matrix cracking. After these matrix cracking propagated a certain distance, due to the extra load transferred from the cracked matrix, the fiber start to randomly fail. However, the final fail of the composite is caused by the stress concentration interaction among these

Fig. 7 Typical fatigue fracture of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite at high applied cyclic stress.

Fig. 8 Fatigue damage at specimen edge of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite at median applied cyclic stress.

Fig. 9 Fatigue damage at specimen center of the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 composite at median applied cyclic stress.

multiple matrix cracking tip. In this region, the fatigue life were controlled by the fatigue crack growth rate in the matrix.

5-2 Fatigue Crack Propagation

Depending on applied ΔK , interfacial bonding strength and matrix toughness, several different fatigue crack propagation behavior were observed in the SCS-6/Ti alloy matrix composites. In the SCS-6/Ti-15-3 and SCS-6/Ti-25-10 composites, crack deflection and branching at the notch-tip along the fiber direction was observed. However, only a single major crack was observed in the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite. Even in the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite, the fatigue crack propagation behavior were quite different at different starting applied ΔK (stress) as shown in Fig. 10. From this figure, three different fatigue crack propagation behaviors were observed in the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite. At high applied ΔK ($49 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$), the crack propagation behavior was similar to the conventional metallic alloy. The crack propagation rate increased as the crack length increased. At medium applied ΔK ($43 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$), the crack propagation rate decreased as the crack length increased. After propagating a certain distance, the crack propagation rate increased again till complete fracture. At low applied ΔK ($37 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$), the initial crack propagation behavior is similar to that of the specimen subjected to medium ΔK . However, instead of increasing in crack propagation rate as fatigue cycles increases, the crack was arrested. Fig. 11 and 12 were optical micrographs for the specimens at applied ΔK of $49 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$ and $37 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, respectively. From Fig. 11, it clearly showed that fibers in the wake of the crack were all broken except the fiber at the crack tip region still bridged the cracked matrix. However, for the low applied ΔK , fiber breakage did not occur, only matrix cracking was observed. The crack arrest phenomenon at the low applied ΔK specimen is due to the fiber bridging effect which will reduce the effective stress concentration at the crack-tip.

6. SUMMARY

From above results, it clearly shows that construction of deformation and damage mechanism maps for the fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite under different mechanical loading are possible. These maps can be used as a basic frame for quantitative theoretical modelling to predict the macroscopic mechanical properties of fiber-reinforced metal matrix composite. Also, a thorough understanding of the microstructural parameters that affect the deformation and damage mechanisms can be used to guide the design of new composite systems and selections of processing parameters.

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Fig. 10 Fatigue crack length v.s. number of fatigue cycles of the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite.

Fig. 11 Fatigue crack propagation damage of the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite at high applied ΔK .

Fig. 12 Fatigue crack propagation damage of the SCS-6/Ti-6-4 composite at low applied ΔK .

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Table I Interfacial properties of fiber-reinforced Ti alloy matrix composite

Composite	Interfacial bonding strength [MPa]	Frictional stress [MPa]
SCS-6/Ti-15-3 (as-fabricated)	124±6	82±4
SCS-6/Ti-15-3 (500 °C/50 hr)	167±12	133±10
SCS-6/Ti-6-4	156±11	88±6
SCS-6/Ti-25-10	115±4	59±2
B ₄ C/B/Ti-6-4	275±45	